

WATER-SOLUBLE POLYMERIC MATERIALS FOR ORGANIC ELECTRONICS

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The objects of the study were PVA film of 16/1 grade (GOST 10779-78), PVA film with an additive of polyhydroxylated fullerene (fullerenol) $C_{60}(OH)_{44}$ (nanocomposite PVA + $C_{60}(OH)_{44}$) with fullerenol concentration of 2 wt.% and PVA film with NaCl additive (composite PVA + NaCl). The concentration of sodium chloride was 4 and 10 wt.%. The thickness of the films was 40–60 μm . All films were produced by pouring aqueous solutions onto the glass surface. It should be noted here that when making PVA + NaCl films with NaCl concentration of 10% and more, crystallized salt appeared on the surface of the films. The films lost elasticity, became brittle and were unsuitable for dielectric measurements. The PVA films with 4% salt added retained elasticity, remained transparent and salt did not appear on their surface. The electrical resistance of all investigated films was measured at constant voltage using a teraohmmeter at room temperature. The specific resistance ρ of the initial PVA film determined based on these measurements was $\sim 6 \cdot 10^{12}$ Ohm·m. The ρ value of the composite film PVA + $C_{60}(OH)_{44}$ was nearly the same. Addition of 4 wt.% salt to PVA reduced ρ to the value of $\sim 3 \cdot 10^{10}$ Ohm·m, i.e. reduced it almost a hundred times. However, when the NaCl concentration was increased to 10%, the resistivity of the film decreased insignificantly and was $\sim 9 \cdot 10^{10}$ Ohm·m. Thus, there was a limiting concentration of NaCl salt, estimated by us as $\sim 4\%$, at which the conductivity of PVA + NaCl composite film significantly increased, but the films retained their mechanical properties. Therefore, we further studied dielectric properties only of films with NaCl concentration of 4%.

Dielectric spectra of the studied films in the frequency range of 0.01–100 Hz are presented in Fig. 2. Two characteristic regions can be distinguished on them, in which the frequency dependences of ϵ' and ϵ'' differ significantly.

In the first (infra-low-frequency) region of the spectrum, at frequencies less than 1 Hz, a rapid increase in dielectric permittivity and dielectric loss factor is observed for all the studied films as the frequency decreases. In this frequency region, the addition of fullerenol to PVA has no appreciable effect on the dielectric parameters of PVA films. However, the addition of NaCl salt to PVA leads to a significant increase in ϵ' and ϵ'' . Note that the lower the voltage frequency, the larger the difference in the values of ϵ' and ϵ'' in PVA + $C_{60}(OH)_{44}$ and PVA + NaCl composites.

At frequencies higher than ~ 1 Hz (the second characteristic region of the spectrum), all investigated films, regardless of the nature of the additives, are characterized by approximately the same and frequency-independent values of ϵ' and ϵ'' .

The results of dielectric properties measurements of water-soluble composite films based on PVA presented in this work show the principal possibility of purposeful change of their parameters: conductivity, dielectric permittivity and dielectric losses. Pure PVA films have high dielectric constant in the low-frequency region of the spectrum, the value of ϵ at a frequency of 0.1 Hz is more than 25, but dielectric losses in this region of the spectrum are very high, which

does not allow the direct use of PVA as a gate dielectric in organic field-effect transistors. The attempt to weaken the interfacial polarization by introducing fullereneol molecules into the intermolecular cavities of PVA cannot be recognized as successful. The composite film PVA + C₆₀(OH)₄₄, while retaining the property of water solubility, does not differ significantly from the PVA film in its dielectric characteristics.

Addition of NaCl salt to PVA leads to a decrease in the resistivity of the obtained composite film by almost two orders of magnitude, to the values $\rho \sim 10^{10}$ Ohm·m. Further reduction of ρ by increasing the concentration of NaCl salt is impossible due to the existence of the limiting concentration of this salt, at which it begins to crystallize on the surface of the film.